

Psychological Correction of Adolescent Aggression

Polina Stolyarova ✉

Independed Researcher, Uzbekistan

Lazizakhon Abbasovna Alidjanova ✉

PhD, Supervisor, IIAU, Uzbekistan

Abstract

Aggression is any behaviour that contains a threat or causes harm to others. It is aimed at insulting or inflicting pain on another person who does not wish for such treatment. Nowadays, adolescent aggression is a global issue. During adolescence, various types of psychological traumas form, leading to the development of aggression. In adolescence, aggression can pose a serious problem, affecting the psychological well-being, social relationships, and academic performance of teenagers. The psychological correction of aggressive behaviour in adolescents is a crucial aspect of their overall development and adaptation. The modern reality forces us to take a new look at the problem of adolescent aggression in society. Aggressive behaviour today is more of a norm than an exception. Nowadays, boys and girls live in an era of rapid oppression by adults. The characteristics of aggressive behaviour are such that, by encroaching on the emotional sphere of the personality, they contribute to the aggravation of moral dissonance and the formation of stressful depressive states. A troubling symptom is the increase in the number of minors with aggressive behaviour, manifested in antisocial actions (alcoholism, vandalism, drug addiction, disorderly conduct, hooliganism, etc.).

Introduction

Today, aggression among adolescents is increasing and, unfortunately, has become commonplace. However, when we talk about adolescent aggression, we encounter more serious problems that affect psychological and mental states. Being in an aggressive state leads to anger, fear, or depression, which reflects on the psychological condition, influencing the overall mood and emotional well-being. Consequently, a person's mental state begins to destabilise, increasing levels of stress and anxiety, leading to the development of mental disorders such as PTSD (post-traumatic stress disorder). These disorders hinder adolescents' adaptation to society, affecting crucial aspects of their lives, such as self-awareness and understanding of their emotions, levels of self-control and confidence, concentration, learning abilities, and relationships with close people. In recent times, this problem forces us to reconsider approaches to adolescents, as it becomes increasingly relevant. Currently, adolescence is a period of active personality formation, where even minor

More Information

How to cite this article: Stolyarova P, Alidjanova LA. Psychological Correction of Adolescent Aggression. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(6):216-8.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(6).28

Keywords:

Adolescent aggression, alcoholism, drug addiction, various types of psychological trauma.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

factors can have long-term consequences. Aggression, as one of the most common manifestations in youth, becomes a serious¹ challenge for us and society, requiring special and effective methods of overcoming it.

Literature Review

Adolescent Aggression Correction

Adolescent aggression is influenced by a variety of factors, including developmental changes during adolescence, environmental stressors, and unmet emotional needs. An important theoretical contribution was made by Ludwig von Bertalanffy, whose general systems theory views aggression as a systemic phenomenon resulting from imbalances in a person's environment. In this model, aggressive behavior is caused by internal conflicts and external stressors such as family dynamics and school pressures.

The Systems Approach

suggests that corrective efforts should aim to restore balance by intervening at multiple levels, including the family and educational institutions.

Other research by Boris Gerasimovich Ananyev emphasizes the importance of biological and age-related changes, especially during adolescence. He advocates an individualized approach that takes into account the biological and psychological characteristics of adolescence [4].

Alexander Leontiev's work on activity and consciousness offers an alternative perspective, linking aggressive behavior to unmet needs and unrealized goals; Leontiev suggests that adolescents can reduce aggression by providing productive activities that help meet their psychological needs. His approach focuses to help adolescents develop self-control and constructive behavior through therapeutic and educational interventions.

Methods for correcting adolescent aggression can be broadly categorized into psychological and pedagogical methods. The most commonly studied methods include cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), social learning, play therapy, and group therapy [5].

Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT): This method aims to help teens eliminate negative thoughts and reduce aggressive behavior by teaching them how to manage their emotions and interactions in a healthier way.

Social learning: teaches teens social skills, empathy, and conflict resolution to help them deal with stressful social situations in a more constructive way.

Play therapy: Play therapy is used to reduce aggression and increase emotional regulation, especially with adolescents who have difficulty expressing their feelings verbally.

Group therapy: Involving young people in groups helps them recognize and cope with aggressive behavior in a supportive environment.

In addition to these traditional methods, new techniques have been developed and tested. One important approach is to integrate systems analysis and look at interactions between adolescents, their families, and schools. This approach allows for an adequate response to external and internal factors contributing to aggression. Interventions are directed not only at the adolescent but also at the adolescent's environment, including family relationships and social interactions at school.

Various methods are used to diagnose aggression and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions. Common diagnostic tools include questionnaires, psychological tests, and observation. These methods help to identify the level of aggression and factors contributing to aggressive behavior and provide a basis for evaluating the results of the intervention.

The effectiveness of intervention techniques is evaluated using comparative analysis, qualitative and quantitative measures. Comparative analysis assesses changes in behavior before and after the intervention; qualitative measures are collected from observations

and quantitative measures from standardized tests and questionnaires.

Professor Sarah-Jayne Blakemore, a Doctor of Psychology, is a leading specialist in adolescent psychology at the University of Cambridge. Sarah-Jayne actively researches adolescent aggression and develops methods for its correction. Professor Blakemore specialises in the external and internal factors influencing aggressive behaviour in adolescents. To determine the characteristics and psychological conditions for correcting aggressive behaviour in adolescence [6].

- To identify the psychological characteristics of aggressive behaviour in adolescence.
- To identify types of aggressive behaviour personalities in adolescence.

Adolescents from general education schools and public places.

Methodology

The methodological basis of the research consists of a set of general psychological principles, among which the systemic approach at the general scientific level holds particular significance (Ludwig von Bertalanffy, B. G. Ananyev, A. N. Leontiev, and others).

Discussion and Results

Ludwig von Bertalanffy was one of the founders of the general theory of systems, considering aggression as a systemic phenomenon caused by the interaction of various components such as psychological, biological, and social.

He viewed adolescent aggression as a result of systemic imbalance.

An essential aspect was the interaction of the adolescent with their environment, where aggressive behaviour could be triggered by external stresses and internal conflicts. He identified all factors contributing to aggression. An essential task was to intervene in the interaction with the aggressor, family, and school.

The main goal was to restore systemic balance through therapeutic and social measures. Boris Ananyev was known for his research on the influence of biological, psychological, and social factors on personality development, focusing on age. Boris Gerasimovich considered adolescent aggression as part of an age crisis. It was important to consider biological changes during puberty.

An individualised approach was used, considering the unique characteristics of each adolescent with aggression.

Psychological counselling and support were vital parts of addressing the age crisis. Special attention was paid to developing self-regulation and emotional resilience through cognitive-behavioural therapy. Alexander Nikolaevich Leontiev was renowned for his research in the field of activity and consciousness, viewing behaviour as goal achievement. Aggression was seen as

a result of unmet needs. An important part was analysing the goals and motives underlying aggressive behaviour. Changing the motivation of adolescents by introducing productive activities into their daily lives. Significant work was done on setting and achieving positive goals. Essential skills such as self-control and constructive behaviour were developed through training or therapeutic groups.

Based on the aforementioned achievements, it can be confidently stated that each scholar contributed to understanding and correcting aggressive behaviour in adolescents. Their approaches were united by attention to systemic analysis, intervention, and an individualised approach, enabling them to effectively address aggression through personality development in adolescents.

Psychological correction of aggression in adolescents showed exceptionally positive results among all participants of this study. The use of methods such as group sessions and individual consultations contributed to reducing manifestations of aggression and increasing levels of self-control. Adolescents who participated in this program demonstrated a decrease in physical and verbal aggression and improved their interpersonal relationships.

The research also highlighted the importance of early support from parents and schools. The results showed that involving parents contributed to more sustainable changes in adolescent behavior. Group sessions helped adolescents develop skills in constructive communication and conflict resolution, positively impacting their behavior.

Conclusion

The results of this study are consistent with global data on the problems of aggression among adolescents. According to WHO (World Health Organization), the presence of violence among adolescents leads to the emergence of aggression, resulting in numerous injuries and, ultimately, can lead to death [1]. Annually, there were 176,000 murders among young people starting at age 15, accounting for 37% of total murders [2]. Violence and aggression can manifest in physical assault or bullying, leading to long-term psychological and physical health problems [3]

Correction of aggression in adolescents using these methods can significantly reduce the risks associated

with moral and physical violence. It can be noted that approaches involving support from parents and teachers had the most significant effect. It is essential to remember that programs aimed at reducing aggression should consider all complex problems such as individual factors, family factors, and social risk factors.

The research results emphasize the importance of including different approaches to correcting aggression in adolescents, incorporating methods such as cognitive-behavioral therapy, group and individual sessions with active participation of parents of aggressive adolescents. Reducing aggression in adolescents will significantly improve not only their health but also create a safe and healthy environment for society, including both adult and young representatives.

References

- [1] World Health Organization (WHO). Youth violence [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; [cited 2024 Jun 15]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/violenceprevention/youth>
- [2] World Health Organization (WHO). Violence against children [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; [cited 2024 Jun 15]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/violenceprevention/child>
- [3] World Health Organization (WHO). Mental health of adolescents [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; [cited 2024 Jun 15]. Available from: https://www.who.int/mental_health/adolescents
- [4] Blakemore SJ. Psikhologo-pedagogicheskaya korrektsiya agressivnogo povedeniya v podrostkovom vozraste [Internet]. CyberLeninka; [cited 2024 Jun 15]. Available from: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/psihologo-pedagogicheskaya-korrektsiya-agressivnogo-povedeniya-v-podrostkovom-vozraste/viewer>
- [5] Agresiya i destruktivnoe povedenie. Psikhologicheskaya gazeta [Internet]. Psy.su; [cited 2024 Jun 15]. Available from: <https://psy.su>
- [6] Psikhologo-istoricheskiy aspekt izucheniya proyavleniya agressii [Internet]. CyberLeninka; [cited 2024 Jun 15]. Available from: <https://cyberleninka.ru>

